

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Combined Effects of Polyethylene Microplastics and Chromium on Growth Parameters, Haemato-Biochemistry, and the Erythrocytic Morphology of Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

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Microplastics being ubiquitously present in aquatic environments raises concern about the well-being of the organisms upon ingestion. Additionally, due to the large surface area and hydrophobicity, these materials adsorb pollutants on their surface which may increase the bioavailability and pose additional health impacts on organisms. Heavy metals, metallic compounds with higher molecular weight and density, exert negative consequences on organisms beyond their tolerable limit and have the tendency to be absorbed on the surface of microplastics. The present study investigates the impacts of single and co-exposure to polyethylene microplastics and chromium on the growth, hemato-biochemical parameters, and morphology of erythrocytes on Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Fish were exposed to four treatments: control (C), polyethylene-5 mg/L (M), 10% 9h-LC₅₀ of Cr (H), and the combination of polyethylene and chromium (MH) for 28 days with 3 replications. The weight gain was lowest in the MH group. Throughout the study period RBC, hemoglobin, and hematocrit showed a decreasing trend in M and MH groups compared to C; while WBC, glucose, and MCV increased with the progression of time. Besides, micronucleus and notch nuclei showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the M and MH groups compared to the C group. Among erythrocytic cellular abnormalities, elongated and twin exhibited similar augmentation. It can be inclusively concluded that combined exposure to polyethylene microplastics and Cr poses serious negative impacts on the growth and blood biomarkers of Nile tilapia.

Keywords: Emerging contaminants, blood biomarkers, multiple stressors, chronic toxicity, fish.